

Shaping Unpredictability: Computational Agents and Emerging Musical Forms¹

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Resta lo spiraglio
del quasi fotografico pittore ad ammonirci
che se qualcosa fu non c'è distanza
tra il millennio e l'istante, tra chi apparve
e non apparve, tra chi visse e chi
non giunse al fuoco del suo cannocchiale. E' poco
e forse è tutto.
Montale, E (1977) · I miraggi · Quaderno di quattro anni

Abstract

This paper explores the design of computational agents for musical improvisation as an extension of human memory and creative process. Starting from *màkina2* (1996), the author reflects on the evolution of his artistic practice in relation to philosophical, neurological, and technological dimensions of time, memory, and unpredictability. Systems such as *Autoimpro* and *Ottetto* integrate real-time interaction, non-deterministic programming, and feedback mechanisms, establishing hybrid cognitive environments where human and machine co-create sound narratives. These works suggest that improvisation is not merely real-time composition but a complex interplay between embodied memory, automated behavior, and emergent structures shaped by dynamic interrelations. Musical time becomes a malleable material, in which the past is continually reinterpreted and transformed by agents acting as mirrors and distorters of human memory.

Keywords: musical improvisation, computational agents, memory, musical time, extended cognition, feedback, human-machine interaction, non-deterministic programming, emergent form, artificial intelligence

Resumen

Este artículo examina el diseño de agentes computacionales para la improvisación musical como una extensión de la memoria humana y del proceso creativo. A partir de *màkina2* (1996), el autor reflexiona sobre la evolución de su práctica artística en relación con dimensiones filosóficas, neurológicas y tecnológicas del tiempo, la memoria y la imprevisibilidad. Sistemas como *Autoimpro* y *Ottetto* integran la interacción en tiempo real, la programación no determinista y la retroalimentación para configurar entornos cognitivos híbridos donde humanos y máquinas co-crean narrativas sonoras. Estas obras proponen que la improvisación no es simplemente composición en tiempo real, sino un entramado complejo entre memoria corporal, comportamiento automatizado y estructuras emergentes modeladas por interacciones dinámicas. El tiempo musical se convierte así en una materia moldeable donde el pasado es reinterpretado y transformado constantemente por agentes que actúan como espejos deformantes de la memoria humana.

Palabras clave: improvisación musical, agentes computacionales, memoria, tiempo musical, cognición extendida, retroalimentación, interacción humano-máquina, programación no determinista, forma emergente, inteligencia artificial

¹ This text is a slightly modified version of the lecture I delivered as part of the series *Improvise con Ñ*: <https://17instituto.org/catedra-improvisar/>, where this and other talks can be accessed.

The Act of Improvisation from a Hybrid Perspective

Following an extended period dedicated to the creation of works for fixed media, in 1996 I composed *màkina2* (Berenguer, 1996), commissioned by the *Groupe de Musique Expérimentale de Bourges* (Verrier, 2005). This is a live electroacoustic piece for electric guitar and NeXT computer, whose principal compositional aim is the computational generation of a complex sonic flow, for which the performer must ultimately be held responsible. *màkina2*, which in fact consists of a computer application written in Max 2.5.2—the last version of this language to run on NeXT—produces no sound unless it receives an audio input. It therefore depends entirely on the sonic activity of the human presence who occupies the stage with their instrument. The guitar's sound is transformed in its entirety through the use of the well-known *FTS* and *ISPW* libraries developed at *IRCAM* for real-time audio processing. The application itself includes a guide, conceived as an open score, whose flexible indications invite the performer to improvise on certain parameters throughout the temporal intervals structuring the piece. The overall temporal structure—strictly determined by the score-guide and by the program implementing it—is, however, not improvised.

By that time, I no longer regarded free improvisation merely as a musical medium which, for various reasons, I had practiced until the early 1980s—most notably with the *Cuarteto Albano* (who did not hesitate to employ the term free improvisation despite our aspirations toward composition). When I composed *màkina2*, I had already come to perceive improvisation as a philosophical and cultural act, a symbol of resistance to the growing structural rigidity I observed not only in electroacoustic music and the so-called contemporary or “new” music, but also in other artistic practices. My interest in musical improvisation developed concurrently with my engagement in sound-related disciplines such as performance and installation art. Yet perhaps due to the very fact that this cultural field was rapidly expanding at the time, I often had the impression that what proliferated most were manifestations I considered superficial or trivial. Despite the immense creative potential I associated with free improvisation—as well as my recognition of the outstanding work of many improvisers whom I invited to perform in events I curated (Berenguer, 2013), such as Chris Cutler, Wade Mathews, Pauline Oliveros, Zeena Parkins, Lê Quan Ninh, Jane Rigler, and John Zorn—many improvisation sessions were shaped not only by musical concerns, but also by the interplay of divergent personal expectations among participants. Too often, these sessions devolved into clashes of egos.

I returned to free improvisation at the end of the 1990s, when the fever surrounding it appeared to be subsiding. When the *Trio Collectif* invited me, together with Eduardo Polonio and Thomas Bjelkeborn, the approach initiated with *màkina2* no longer felt like a singular experience confined to the past. Rather, it marked a new point of departure in a creative path that I continue to explore—both in musical performance and in audiovisual installations, where, for me, the interplay between predictability and unpredictability is not only inherent to the process, but an essential condition for its development.

Memory and Time in the Creative Process

All the works discussed in this paper stem from a critique of time management in dominant concert settings. I am fully aware that, ultimately, time management is a political matter from which the prevailing conception of what a concert should be

derives. Both spatial and temporal management are shaped by the inertias through which power is expressed within each cultural field. For now, I will simply say that, in this sense, I find concerts of pre-fixed music as questionable as many of improvised music. In both cases, the underlying structure is the unidirectionality of discourse from the emitter (the performers) to the receiver (the listeners), much like in a religious mass or other situations I shall—albeit abusively—refer to as shamanic, where officiants deliver spiritual discourses to their audience.

In fact, with regard to consciousness, which governs our perception of time and whose localization remains a matter of debate, I am compelled to ask whether it exists solely in the present. Is there consciousness without memory? For this reason, I feel obliged to assert that, for me, improvised music does not occur exclusively in the time of its emergence.

Any material heard in an improvisation has a prior history. It does not arise from nothing. It has been constructed, sound by sound, before it acquires form at the moment of improvisation—perhaps different from its earlier versions, perhaps not appreciably so. Instrumental gestures, sounds, musemes (that is, atomic formal elements of music), derive from more or less extensive developments that have taken place in the inner time of each improviser, as processes of crystallization of those musemes within their neuromuscular system. These processes manifest not merely as automatic, but as automated behaviors stored in implicit memory. The improviser requires a certain period to refine the execution of materials derived from their musical ideas. At that point, memory intervenes—an essential component of any human activity. Memory is also present at the moment of choosing which materials to execute in simultaneity with others—whether those just performed or yet to come. Memory thickens the present (Leipp, 1977). Without it, simultaneity would not be perceived. In that prior crystallization process, associative memory plays a key role. With the help of active listening, it is initially trained through fully conscious and voluntary processes, which become increasingly unconscious until they appear automatic. A general issue in performance, improvised or not, is the interplay between conscious and unconscious activity—between voluntary and involuntary actions. One can be equally aware of either type of behavior—or unaware of both. Experiments such as those by Soon et al. (2008), which, based on functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) and machine learning, analyze patterns of brain activity (especially in areas such as the prefrontal and parietal cortex), have shown that it is possible to predict simple decisions up to 7 seconds before the subject becomes aware of them. Regardless of this awareness, part of the ultimate decision-making process is unconscious. We do not fully know what leads us to choose a particular material in an improvisation. One major interpretive challenge is to maintain awareness of gesture, no matter how crystallized or automated it may have become. Consciousness, as an optimal machine for the emergence of new ideas and patterns—patterns elusive to both rigid order and absolute chaos—shifts focus according to the persistence of internal and external signals. The description of consciousness as a chaotic attractor integrating multiple temporalities is not new in neuroscience and supports the claim that our perception of musical time is profoundly nonlinear.

Many important contributions to the study of consciousness converge on the notion of the self as a fragmentary multiplicity, closely aligned with the discontinuous flow of time. We experience the constant change in states of consciousness as evidence of the passage of time.

There is extensive neurophysiological and psychological literature on attention, consciousness, and automatism, which I will not explore here in depth. I will only note that automatism relates anatomically to the extrapyramidal system, so called because it lies just outside the pyramids of the *medulla oblongata*, which conduct signals responsible for voluntary movement.

Although it is meaningless to speak of music that is fully pre-fixed—since no musical notation system can capture everything that occurs during the emergence of any music—we might allegorically describe such music as a kind of sculpture or semi-crystal of time made of sound. I will again take a liberty of language and refer to fully notated or fixed music as that which traditionally arises from the interpretation of a detailed score. In such cases, the score functions as a form of memory—an external memory. Yet, just as in fully fixed music, memory plays a crucial role in improvisation, both in the construction of materials and in their emergence in time and space. The memory of *musemes* employed in improvisation is the same memory that allows a performer of fully notated music to recall an entire score.

In the processes of memory retrieval—regardless of the nature of the memory—what rationalist influence has termed "errors" often arise. It is notable that this also occurs in many biological processes, such as protein synthesis or nucleic acid replication, where mistakes or chance events can lead to the formation of new proteins. This may hinder or facilitate certain life processes. This is a well-known topic in molecular genetics: such errors are part of the mechanisms evolution uses in natural selection. The memory systems of the nervous system share this trait. Error is not only intrinsic to our nature—it is intrinsic to nature itself, to reality itself; so much so that perhaps what we call errors are not errors at all.

The workings of memory resemble the game of telephone: a source of misunderstandings, but also of long-term insights that can be exploited by serendipity. Due to this instability, García Márquez (2002) could write that life "...is not what one lived, but what one remembers and how one remembers it in order to tell it."

Neither improvisation nor composition is exempt from this property of memory, and it is partly because of it that materials undergo evolutionary transformations, giving rise to new sonic and musical domains. I find this process desirable. It aligns with what is called development in musical form. In both improvisation and the performance of pre-fixed music, development is a crucial factor for reaching the consciousness of listeners and performers alike, as it sustains attention—and thus brings improvisation and composition closer together. For all these reasons, I reject the notion of free improvisation as composition in real time. It is a form of composition, yes, but not in real time. The improviser composes, and the composer improvises. In both cases, we are dealing with people (musicians) who construct the materials that will later become part of their concerted emergences—whether entirely fixed or entirely unfixed. Between these two poles, as Wilfrido Terrazas (Lomnitz, 2025) mentioned in the first lecture, we can find numerous intermediate forms. For this reason, I find it extraordinarily difficult—and indeed unnecessary—to establish a clear distinction between the two practices.

In improvisation, the instability of human memory is usually positive when it results in the development of materials, as it allows the musical flow to evolve constantly, thereby stimulating attentive listening in both performers and audiences. What is less desirable is the limitation of memory, which constrains the improviser's expressive range and thus the variability of their output. This is one of the structural reasons why collective

participation is crucial. We must recognize that the universality of musical time experience is an illusion—a social, cultural illusion. While isolated durations between significant events may appear continuous, the actual experience of musical time is fragmented and articulated, filled with markers and reference points, laden with meanings that—being ineffable—reside in mental spaces often beyond language. Hence, collective musical improvisation can be understood as a set of sonic emergences resulting from the convergence of individual memories and individual times that constitute a multidimensional collective time, where listening serves as the entry point and analytical mechanism. In such a context, the spatiotemporal relations between each participant's materials tend to be less predictable than the materials themselves. Collective improvisation should therefore offer a higher degree of innovation and surprise than individual improvisation, leading to renewed experiences for both listeners and performers, and thus achieving the status of collective sonic narrative.

It seems to be a shared sentiment among improvisers—and a widespread practice, likely stemming from jazz culture, which I would describe as nomadic or itinerant—to perform in constantly shifting and diverse formations. For this reason, I believe that stable improvisation groups, such as the aforementioned Trio Collectif or the *ABC Trio* (Gustavo Alcaraz, Gonzalo Biffarella, Julio Catalano), motivated of course by an interest in strengthening collective bonds, but also in enriching the content of their improvisations while preserving their identity, engage in improvisation sessions with other improvisers—among whom I have had the great fortune, pleasure, and honor to count myself.

Improvisational Abilities of Machines

It is a well-established fact that silicon-based memories are more stable than biological ones, and their horizon of limits is considerably broader. The memory of a traditional computational machine thus possesses capabilities that complement those of humans, and such features can be beneficially integrated into improvisational sessions in which it participates. A computational device endowed with substantial memory capacity can store as much or more information than a group of human improvisers. Moreover, with appropriate programming, it can flexibly transform the contents of its memory to generate new materials that are themselves susceptible to further storage. Although these transformations do not occur in the same way they do in humans, I do not find them lacking in interest. They can be effectively modulated according to the specifications or needs of those interacting with the device, while its memory stability—which only expands—is not compromised. The presence of such a device in an improvisation session could mitigate the memory limitations of a solo improviser while emulating their abilities to transform musical material.

Despite its capacity as a creative performer that transforms and varies sonic material in real time, our device—for now, at least—falls short of matching the emotional and relational capabilities of the human group. Regardless of how much it may draw upon the effectiveness of computational techniques such as machine learning, including high-density neural networks made famous by the emergence of *ChatGPT* and now *DeepSeek*, it lacks motivation, will, and desire—qualities that remain, for now, difficult to engineer. Reinforcement learning techniques such as *Q-learning*, *Proximal Policy Optimization* (PPO), and *Deep Q-Networks* (DQN), which simulate reward or punishment scenarios, do not go beyond simulation. They simulate, but they do not signify. They are not real implementations capable of compromising or enhancing the physical or mental integrity of a machine devoid of survival instinct. A deeper inquiry into meaning is required. This, for now, marks a fundamental distance between us and the machines. More than mere

desire, it is what Schopenhauer (1844/2009) termed the “will to will.” In any human activity, the will is rooted beyond the activity itself. Likewise, in music, desire is not limited to the materials or their interactions within that allegorical semi-crystal of time I attribute to musical form. Yet the limitation arising from the absence of will does not mean that the participation of computational devices in improvisation sessions cannot generate indisputably musical situations fully compatible with the expectations of human improvisers and their audiences—particularly since human participation in such applications already presupposes the presence of will. I believe this is clearly manifested in my recent experiments applying what we call artificial intelligence to improvisation and composition. I will speak about these shortly, but I would first like to reflect on an intermediate stage.

As a result of a fruitful collaboration with Gonzalo Biffarella, I conceived an application that composes without temporal limitation based on a set of five improvisations we carried out remotely during the pandemic, made possible by *QuackTrip*—Miller Puckette’s (2020) contribution implementing *JackTrip* in *Pure Data*, which I would describe as an apologetic gloss on *A Declaration of the Independence of Cyberspace* (Barlow, 1996). Gonzalo produced a fixed version by mixing the recordings (Biffarella & Berenguer, 2021), while I created a generative one, capable of sounding indefinitely (Berenguer & Biffarella, 2021).

Was it composing or improvising? To me, it makes little difference, as I perceive few distinctions between the two. What does seem evident is that the sound sculpture emerges in real time whenever the application is activated; and its productions, although significantly distinct from one another, are recognizable thanks to their materials and the seed-like formal structures, gestures, of each generation in meso-time—alternating tensions based sometimes on intensity, at other times on density, speed, timbral qualities, etc., or on combinations of these and other parameters. But it never ends, unless disconnected. This has a profound impact on form.

The Machine as Prosthesis

As previously noted, *màkina2* does virtually nothing unless it receives input from the performer. Compared with what is commonly referred to as mixed electroacoustic music, this is a significant distinction. In mixed music, the electronic component functions independently from the performers of the non-electronic instruments involved. It may rely on fixed media playback, software execution, or similar means, but there is always a dedicated musical operator responsible exclusively for the electronic part. This also contrasts with what is known as *live electronics*, where non-electronic instruments—though subject to live processing—do not exert control over how their sound is transformed, as that responsibility falls to a musician other than the performer.

In *màkina2*, the programming dictates that the audio input from the performer ultimately determines the sonic behavior of the entire application. Their decisions, therefore, condition the overall characteristics of the resulting sound object. Responsibility for the sonic construction lies equally with the programmer—who composes and writes the code—and with the performer, who, through their execution, can profoundly influence the outcome. Clark and Chalmers (1998) argue that the mind is not confined to the brain or body but extends into the external environment through tools, technologies, and other interactive elements. From this perspective, *màkina2*, which extends the performer’s instrument and can influence their decisions as much as it is influenced by them, can be considered an instance of extended cognition: the

performer's consciousness is distributed across the computational system. The flow of information (gestures, responses, sounds) generates a shared space in which the creative act takes place.

Despite the initial score-guide, both in my own performances and those by flutist Jane Rigler, we discovered that detailed study of the machine's possible responses to our input allowed us to go much further, using the very sonic outcomes of the programming as suggestions for shaping our interventions. This created a loop.

Since then, the idea of the computationally expanded instrument has haunted me—an idea embedded in the foundations of the applications I present here, designed from the outset as improvisational systems based on interaction between humans and machines, supported by the automated manipulation of sonic databases. The main difference between *Memorias de la distancia* and subsequent applications lies in the fact that the database—or parts of it—is generated, analyzed, and responded to in *real time*, crystallizing temporally into sonic emergence.

These applications aim to produce music algorithmically, colored by certain behavioral traits of human improvisers. I have always been struck by how improvisers sometimes repeat, gloss, support, or transform segments of each other's discourse, while at other times they develop their own lines of expression, diverging significantly from the general flow. These applications are, in fact, live systems. *Autoimpro* (Berenguer, 2022) was initially conceived to continuously listen and record one or more performers in order to provide them with musemes based on their own output. It offers improvisational suggestions generated by a group of relatively independent computational agents whose strategy is to monitor each other's actions. Each agent, with a probability greater than 0.5, selects a segment of around one minute from previously recorded material, close to those chosen by the other seven agents, and transforms it—by transposition, fragmentation, or filtering—before reintroducing it into the general audio stream. The rest of the time, it selects a playback point at random, ignoring the actions of the other agents. Regarding the use of randomness, I refer to its two traditional interpretations. In a deterministic (Laplacean) worldview, randomness is a measure of our ignorance of the causes behind an event. In a non-deterministic cosmology, such as that derived from quantum mechanics, randomness is intrinsic to nature itself. Either interpretation justifies decisions made by chance.

The result is a dynamic system composed of eight coupled oscillators (Berenguer, 2007), whose rules generate a multiplicity of situations, all rooted in the manipulation of the human performer's sonic past. *Autoimpro* differs from *Memorias de la distancia* in that its agents reproduce segments of recordings made live, thus manipulating the recent past of the improviser. These agents are not passive tools but active extensions of human memory and creativity. This interaction forms a hybrid cognitive system, where creativity emerges from the dialogue between the human and the machinic. The agents act as external, transformative memory. They externalize human memory and return it enriched. This raises questions about who remembers and how the past is reinterpreted. Are we witnessing a redefinition of the boundaries of the self? If the mind extends into the environment, where does human execution end? Is it the complete system (performer + agents) that performs? If improvisation arises not solely from human performance but from the dynamic coupling of human and machine, must this then be considered a case of creativity as a distributed process and collective act?

These applications operate through feedback relationships. Feedback is a crucial concept in any cybernetic framework. It occurs universally. It is a general dynamic principle applicable to creative processes such as improvisation. If the brain activity underlying an individual performer's decisions operates through positive and negative feedback loops across all levels of their neurocognitive apparatus, then the interactions between participants in an improvisational or composed musical session are similarly established through feedback across their respective temporal flows. While feedback is present even in performances of composed music—manifesting in the co-construction of shared tempo, tuning, and dynamics—in improvisation, this resource becomes even more critical. In both cases, feedback is mediated by listening, which provides evaluative input. The family of computational applications derived from *màkina2* exemplifies human-machine collaboration based on improvisations emerging from multiple cross-feedback loops. When a machine interacts live with a performer, it becomes part of an extended cognitive process, precisely due to the feedback between its discourse and the human's. In this context, there are 72 feedbacks. One cannot say the performer is alone; their creative thought is extended, augmented, or expanded by the technological system they use and simultaneously embody.

Both *màkina2* and *Autoimpro* are based on non-deterministic programming. Modifications to the input from the non-electronic instrument may not immediately affect system behavior. A delay in response may or may not occur. As a result, the performer is often required to anticipate the overall behavior of the application solely through their own execution. These are systems that demand constant monitoring of their potential trajectories. Excessive positive feedback may lead to saturation, just as excessive negative feedback tends to produce rarefaction. In such interactions, feedback conditions the mesoform of the sonic semi-crystal, an attractor of a well-defined dynamic system based on coupled oscillation. The non-human thereby influences the formal decisions from which the sonic discourse emerges.

Time as a Material for Creation

In systems such as *màkinaN* (Berenguer, 2019), *Ottetto* (Berenguer, 2025), and others, the computer partakes in the chaotic game. The agents respond in a non-deterministic manner, maintaining fluid interaction both among themselves and with the human performer. The result is an extended improvisation, where machine and human co-organize into emergent sonic attractors. From the agent behavior programming—based on stochastic filtering—emerges the concept of designing unpredictability, itself rooted in earlier experiments conducted with Lluís Callejo (Berenguer, 2011) in the late 1970s, aimed at simulating the avoidance-avoidance conflict experienced by a laboratory rat punished regardless of its choice. Our program eventually reached a point of paralysis. Underlying that experience was the notion of neurosis as a cadential element, as a fundamental motor of form, capable of determining the moment of cadence.

In *Ottetto*, after the initial stimulus from a human performer or a recording, eight computational agents influence each other and the input signal across eight solos, 28 duos, 56 trios, 70 quartets, 56 quintets, 28 sextets, eight septets, and one octet. *Ottetto* emerges from software built upon the Dicy2 library (Nika, J., Muller, A., Borg, J., Ostrowski, M., & Assayag, G., 2022). It also implements eight improvising agents. Each one listens to the audio signals of the human improvisation and the other agents, takes into account their sonic and musical descriptors, and attempts to intervene with fragments from its own prior repertoire whose descriptors are compatible with those recently analyzed. This repertoire consists of recordings from a human performance. In

this version, these are recordings of human inputs in *Autoimpro* interacting with responses from the application, which in turn expose the human to their own modified recent past, thus conditioning their execution, now reinterpreted by the agents of *Ottetto* months later in response to the stimulus of a new improvisation.

If, in everyday life, our present actions and decisions are dependent on the reinterpretation of our past, here, computational agents and the guitarist, the clarinetist, or whoever the performer may be, collaborate in a similar process mediated by algorithms. A new layer of meaning emerges wherein the agents act as proxies for older memories, reinterpreting and transforming previous material originally generated by a conscious human who now responds creatively—completing the loop, if successful, or spiraling toward infinity. As Montale (1977) suggests, our memories are mirages—reinterpretations of the past that change over time. *Ottetto* invokes the mirage as a metaphor of remembrance. Its agents act as distorting mirrors of the improviser, returning to them their own transformed temporal image. "Il tempo si ravvolge in sé stesso", as Montale wrote in *I miraggi*, where images arise as distorted memories or illusions of the past in a time that recycles itself recursively into new forms. Time and form, in this reverberation, become infinite. Not coincidentally, the reverberation of spaces is also memory.

In normal listening circumstances, the leap of consciousness to the past or future—whether personal or musical—is inevitable. So too is the sudden excursion into the timeless realm of abstract ideas. Past, present, and future are interconnected in consciousness. In musical improvisation, the experience of time manifests in how musicians (human and/or machine) respond creatively to what has just occurred or occurred long ago, directing it toward something new. Montale and Bergson (1889, 1907) dismantle the illusion of linear time, that hierarchical sequentiality so common in notated music, laden with authoritarianism and didacticism. Following the path set by those authors and others, *Ottetto* and *Autoimpro*, whose agents become distorting mirrors and generators of memory mirages, treat musical time as a malleable, cyclical material dependent on human-machine interaction, such that past and future (in terms of prediction or teleology) become active parts of the present. Montale uses poetry to explore memory as a process of recreation, not reproduction. Similarly, these applications can be interpreted as sonic allegories of the continuous reconfiguration of memories, opening the door to the idea of improvisation as a reflection of the lability of memory, of life, and of the universe itself.

Bringing back transformed fragments of what has already occurred—recurrence of the past in the present—creates a spiral time in which the human and non-human intertwine to produce something new. This is not merely a mechanically stored past, but one made malleable and reinvented in the present. Through memory, time itself becomes an improviser. These works are, for me, memory and narrative, where the human and non-human are interwoven in an intellectual exploration made music.

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² I regret the need to cite myself so frequently. It is not my usual practice. However, the fact that this text concerns my own work provides justification.

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